

Automated Mangrove Detection Method Using Combined Machine Learning and Mangrove Index Over Indonesia

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(Received September 27, 2024; Revised February 06, 2025; Accepted April 01, 2025)

Abstract: Indonesia possesses approximately 22.6% of the world's mangrove ecosystem. The country's mangroves exhibit diverse characteristics, both in terms of their growing environment and species variety. This ecosystem serves as a vital habitat for numerous species of birds, fish, crabs, and other organisms, significantly contributing to global biodiversity. However, mangrove mapping in Indonesia is still primarily conducted on a local scale within individual regions or provinces. Consequently, there is a need for a comprehensive mangrove detection method that can facilitate national-scale mapping, making the process more effective and efficient. Integration of satellite data which covers a wide area and machine learning can obtain mangrove detection to be faster and more accurate. The study proposes an automated mangrove detection method using a combined mangrove index and machine learning over Indonesia. Normalized Difference Moisture Index and Mangrove Vegetation Index from Landsat 8/9 images were used to obtain training datasets for the Random Forest process. The results show that the overall accuracy is 0.93, and the kappa accuracy is 0.91. It proves that the proposed method can be used for mapping mangroves and non-mangroves accurately.

Keywords: difference random forest; Landsat 8; Landsat 9; machine learning; mangrove; mangrove vegetation index; normalized difference moisture index

1. Introduction

Mangroves are valuable ecosystems that offer various benefits, including natural protection, economic resources, tourism opportunities, and ecological support¹. They are efficient ecosystems located at the interface of land and sea². Mangroves are found in approximately 137,600 square kilometers of coastal areas in 118 countries worldwide³. These forests typically consist of shrubs and trees that grow in wetland conditions along tropical and subtropical coastlines⁴. Restoring mangrove forests for coastal defense is significantly more cost-effective than traditional infrastructure like breakwaters⁵. Additionally, mangroves help regulate water quality, and it's estimated

that a small area of mangrove forest can process waste from a larger area of aquaculture operations⁶. Mangroves also store carbon more efficiently than terrestrial forests due to the carbon-rich soil⁷.

Despite increased efforts to restore mangrove forests in recent decades, their cover area and species diversity continue to decline at a rate of 1-2% per year⁸. Regular monitoring of existing mangroves is crucial to track changes in their area and species distribution. This information is vital for making informed decisions about managing potential threats from uncontrolled development and modeling the impact of various factors. Traditional field-based methods can be challenging and time-consuming due to the dense undergrowth and the intertidal

location of mangrove ecosystems⁹). Additionally, these methods are often expensive and have limited coverage. Remote sensing techniques offer a more efficient and cost-effective alternative for mapping mangrove vegetation and understanding the spatial distribution of species. In areas where field surveys are impractical, remote sensing can provide valuable data for monitoring and managing mangrove ecosystems.¹⁰ Field observation and survey methods are time-consuming, expensive, and limited in scope. In mangrove ecosystems where logistical challenges and accessibility issues make complete surveys impractical, remote sensing can be used to map vegetation cover and identify the spatial distribution of species. Remote sensing techniques are widely used to monitor the environment and natural resources over time¹¹). The availability of remote sensing data enables efficient and cost-effective methods for monitoring mangrove forests¹²). Remote sensing studies of mangroves have various objectives, including: Establishing a global baseline for mangrove expansion³); Understanding the status and distribution of mangrove forests worldwide¹³); Evaluating the importance of blue carbon ecosystems¹⁴); Creating a global carbon map for mangrove forest soils¹⁵); Analyzing trends in vegetation indices¹⁶); Using vegetation indices as predictive variables in mangrove classification algorithms¹⁷).

In remote sensing, mangroves can be identified based on the textural and spectral properties of their canopy and leaves¹⁸). Due to the distribution of spongy mesophyll cells, most mangrove species can be distinguished in the visible and near-infrared (NIR) regions¹⁹). By using structural information from various remote sensing products, regional and global estimates can be made regarding mangrove height, canopy, species succession, biomass, and carbon stocks²⁰). Many review studies have recognized the importance of remote sensing in mangrove research²¹). However, most of these studies have not extensively reviewed the application of different spectral indices to mangrove forests.

A spectral index is an equation that combines the pixel values of two or more spectral bands in a multispectral image. They are primarily based on band ratios or feature scaling algorithms (e.g., normalized or standardized algorithms) and offer improved sensitivity for detecting spectral signatures compared to individual spectral bands²²). Spectral indices have significantly contributed to a better understanding of environments and ecosystems across time and space²³). In mangrove remote sensing, spectral indices can be categorized into vegetation spectral indices and mangrove-specific spectral indices²⁴). While vegetation indices have been widely applied to mangrove ecosystems, separating mangroves from other vegetation types using a single vegetation index can be challenging²⁵). To address this, several mangrove-specific spectral indices have been proposed²⁶). Despite the high accuracy of the

Mangrove Vegetation Index (MVI), SWIR reflectance values are often contaminated by noise from the ground, water bodies, and surrounding vegetation (Bhatti & Tripathi, 2014). Additionally, MVI can misclassify mangroves as other land cover types, especially in aquaculture zones, irrigated agricultural land, and palm tree locations²⁷). MVI is a single index that classifies mangroves, terrestrial vegetation, bare land, built-up areas, water, and clouds using reflectance data from Sentinel-2A and Landsat-8. MVI validation has demonstrated an accuracy of more than 80% for all geographic study locations.

Mangrove mapping can be done using supervised or unsupervised, pixel-based or object-based image classification. Previous studies primarily used satellite image composite bands and unsupervised or parametric supervised algorithms to detect mangrove extent without applying spectral indices²⁸). More recent studies have employed mangrove classification using random forest-based spectral indices and achieved the highest overall post-classification accuracy (>92%) (Jiang et al., 2021). The most commonly applied machine learning classification algorithms in remote sensing studies are random forests (RF), artificial neural networks (ANN), and linear and radial support vector machines (SVML, SVMR)²⁹). RF has been shown to be a reliable method for characterizing vegetation³⁰). For mangrove identification, RF has outperformed SVM and RDA methods in estimating mangrove cover in Iran based on LANDSAT imagery³¹).

This study aims to create a highly accurate map of mangrove distribution in Indonesia using a combination of a mangrove index and machine learning. The MVI index and other relevant parameters were used to detect mangroves throughout 2023. Approximately 5,000 data points were randomly split into a 70:30 training and testing ratio. The study area was categorized into four classes: mangrove, water, non-mangrove vegetation, and land, using the random forest algorithm. Machine learning, a type of artificial intelligence that analyzes and identifies patterns in large datasets, was employed for all data processing³²). This approach is expected to be effective in detecting mangroves across Indonesia.

2. Material and Methods

This research utilized Landsat 8 and Landsat 9 imagery hosted on the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform. Landsat 8/9 images are commonly used for various earth monitoring applications, including land use monitoring³³), plantation area mapping³⁴), and geological mapping³⁵). These datasets contain atmospherically corrected surface reflectance derived from data captured by the OLI sensors on Landsat 8 and 9. The images include 5 visible and near-infrared (VNIR) bands, 2 shortwave infrared (SWIR)

bands, intermediate bands used in ST product calculations, and QA bands. Landsat 8 and 9 SR products are generated using the Land Surface Reflectance Code (LaSRC), a single-channel algorithm developed by the Rochester Institute of Technology (RIT) and NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL). From Landsat 8 and Landsat 9 surface reflectance data, data was selected for the period 1 January 2023 to 31 December 2023, then limited to the Indonesian region and its surroundings. The Landsat 8/9 mosaic image of Indonesia is shown in the Figure 1. The purpose of using surface reflectance data is to ensure that the spectral response value for each object in this study is comparable to the initial value in the field.

Fig. 1: Landsat 8/9 mosaic image of Indonesia in 2023 as input data

Google Earth Engine (GEE) is a cloud-based platform for storing and processing spatial data. It offers a solution for handling large amounts of spatial data efficiently. Unlike traditional methods of downloading and processing satellite images, GEE allows users to process data by writing programming scripts that instruct the platform to perform the desired operations. This approach significantly reduces processing time and enables users to work with extremely large datasets.

In this study, we used the Murray global tidal wetland change to mask the tidal area in Indonesia. The Murray Global Tidal Wetland Change Dataset provides maps of the worldwide distribution and changes in tidal wetlands. The dataset was created by combining data from 1,166,385 Landsat 5 to 8 satellite images with environmental factors like temperature, slope, and elevation that are known to affect the distribution of different ecosystem types³⁶.

The One Map Mangrove (OMM) 2023 is an update from the OMM in the previous year. The preparation of OMM 2023 involves a series of comprehensive stages, i.e the preparation of technical guidelines and interpretation keys, updating of satellite imagery, visual interpretation of images, ground checks, quality control, and data compilation, analysis, and tabulation. In the ground check step, field validation of the mangrove ecosystem in each province in Indonesia is conducted by Basin River Management Agency representatives along with members of the quality control team from the central government. By the end of 2023, the area of mangrove forests in Indonesia was 3.44 million Ha. In the proposed method the OMM 2023 was used as a mangrove dataset.

The research area is classified into four land cover classes,

namely: mangrove, water, non-mangrove vegetation, and soil. The algorithm used in this classification is the random forest algorithm. RF is an ensemble classifier that demonstrates stability to variations in the segmentation scale. Random Forest appears to be effective in selecting object features and can manage high-dimensional data. Numerous studies indicate that, in comparison to other machine learning algorithms, Random Forest is sensitive to the amount of training data and sampling methods³⁷. It demonstrates superior accuracy with an expanded training dataset. RF can effectively operate with diverse mangrove species when employing an object-based methodology. RF is advocated by research for the differentiation of mangrove species. In this study we specified the range of values tested during hyperparameter tuning 100, the method used for the selection random search, and the rationale for choosing the final value. This decision was due to computational efficiency considerations.

A total of 210 sample data points were taken for each land cover class at each sampling location. The sampling locations were chosen randomly in coastal areas of Indonesia. So, the total sample of data points is 5040 sample points which are used to train and test the algorithm with a random ratio of 70:30.

On the other hand, to determine the index to be used in the algorithm, we analyze the spectral response of each object in the training sample. Each class took 1260 samples. Responses are calculated from the median value of each class to avoid extreme values. The spectral responses of the visible, NIR, SWIR1, and SWIR2 bands regarding mangroves, water, soil, and vegetation are shown in Figure 2. In Figure 2 the spectral responses of bands 6 and 7 are able to differentiate well between classes. So, these two bands need to be considered in the elaboration of the algorithm.

Fig. 2: Landsat 8/9 band spectral response to mangrove land cover, water, soil and vegetation

Bands 6 and 7 Landsat 8/9 are SWIR1 and SWIR2, respectively. As a result, it is important to do further analysis of the index that employs these two bands. We examined different indices against the four land cover classes, and the results are displayed in Figure 3. Only MVI and NDMI were shown to be capable of distinguishing mangroves from other vegetation among the

five indices examined. Despite having nearly identical spectral response levels, the other three indices can distinguish between mangroves, water, and soil.

Currently, mangrove detection entails confronting various distinct challenges: Mangroves possess elevated moisture levels due to their presence in coastal and intertidal zones characterized by substantial soil and canopy water content; they frequently have dense canopy formations that may conceal underlying features. blend of vegetation, water, and land.

MVI was developed to mitigate the impact of soil and background reflectance, an essential characteristic for mangrove detection, where mudflats or saline soils could normally disrupt vegetation signals. Furthermore, it exhibits sensitivity to alterations in vegetation. MVI's capacity to manage intricate reflectance allows for more effective differentiation, hence enhancing accuracy.

While NDMI is great at finding out how wet plants are, which makes it perfect for mangroves that do well in wet or muggy conditions. NDMI can help find areas of stressed or damaged mangroves that may not be obvious from general vegetation measures by measuring the amount of water present. The NDMI index does a good job of showing the areas where mangroves meet nearby bodies of water or flora on higher ground.

MVI and NDMI are prioritized in mangrove research due to their distinct benefits in assessing vegetation density, water content, and nuanced alterations in mangrove ecosystems. These features render them more efficient than broad indices such as NDVI or NDWI for precise mapping and monitoring of mangrove ecosystems.

The mangrove class has a greater MVI index value than the vegetation class, and the soil class has the lowest MVI value, although it is not significantly different from the water class. The NDMI index shows nearly identical values for all four classes, although they may still be distinguished. The EVI, Simple Ratio, NDVI, and NDWI indices offer distinct values for soil and water classes but do not clearly distinguish between mangroves and vegetation.

The Mangrove Vegetation Index (MVI) is a specific index used to identify mangroves. It employs the Green, SWIR, and NIR bands. The SWIR band measures water

absorption effectively. Leaf liquid water affected both the SWIR1 and SWIR2 bands. The NIR band measures the greenness in vegetation accurately³⁸⁾. The following formula is used to compute MVI³⁹⁾.

$$MVI = \frac{NIR - GREEN}{SWIR1 - GREEN} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3: Surface reflectance values of mangrove land cover, water, soil, and vegetation on the indices examined

The Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) is a remote sensing tool used to assess moisture levels in vegetation. It utilizes near-infrared (NIR) and short-wave infrared (SWIR) spectral bands to calculate the index. The NDMI is calculated using the following formula:

$$NDMI = \frac{NIR2 - SWIR}{2 \cdot (NIR2 + SWIR)} \quad (2)$$

Landsat 8-9 SR data is produced using the Land Surface Reflectance Code (LaSRC), which employs the coastal aerosol band for aerosol inversion tests, incorporates auxiliary climate data from MODIS or VIIRS CMG, and utilizes a specialized radiative transfer model.

The Landsat 8-9 dataset consists of cloud cover evaluations at the scene and pixel levels. The Quality Assessment (QA) band contains data that identifies clouds, cloud shadows, snow, and clear pixels. We have utilized the QA band for cloud masking processing in the initial phase of the algorithm. In addition, the data used in this study has been sharpened to the spatial resolution of 15.

Fig. 4: Flow chart of the algorithm in this study

Several cloud masking techniques can be applied using Landsat 8 data on GEE. One common approach is leveraging the Quality Assessment (QA) band provided with Landsat 8 imagery. The QA band contains information about cloud and shadow cover, allowing for the identification and subsequent masking of these areas. Additionally, users can explore more sophisticated methods, such as the Fmask algorithm, which employs spectral and spatial characteristics to detect clouds and shadows with higher accuracy. The Fmask cloud masking formula in this research used spectral thresholds as follows

$$Cloud_score = \min \left(\frac{blue-red}{blue+red}, \frac{Blue-SWIR1}{Blue+SWIR1} \right) \quad (3)$$

Median values calculated from multiday Landsat 8 and 9 SR data from 1 January until 31 December 2023 in Indonesia territory. The median values are stored as raster imagery named Landsat 8-9 SR Median. The NDMI and MVI are stored as two layers of raster imagery.

The dataset is created by taking pixel values from the NDMI and MVI layers at each point from each class. There are 1260 points in every class so in total there are 5040 datasets for four classes. It is divided into training and testing with portions of 70% and 30% randomly so that there are 3497 training datasets and 1541 testing points.

The classification model was built using random forest and training datasets. To determine the accuracy of the model, the classification model is tested using a testing dataset.

Based on a good level of accuracy, the model is applied to classify median Landsat 8-9 SR data. The classification results are filtered on areas that intersect with the tidal wetland map sourced from The Murray Global Tidal Wetland Change provided by the Earth engine. Figure 4

shows the algorithm of this study.

3. Results

The global results of this research are shown in Figure 5. This research is limited to the detection of mangrove ecosystems in tidal areas. The mangrove ecosystem is represented by the green area, while other vegetation in the tidal zone is depicted by the yellow area. The blue and gray zones represent the location of water and land in the tidal zone, respectively.

Fig. 5: Mangrove ecosystems detected by the proposed method over Indonesia

Based on Table 1 there are no mangroves that were detected as soil and vice versa. Additionally, the algorithm performs well in detecting the actual land cover of 4 classes. Finally, the classification model built has high accuracy. There is 0.93 overall accuracy and a kappa of 0.91.

Table 1: The confusion matrix shows the model's ability to discriminate mangrove, water, soil, and vegetation classes for land cover prediction. Columns reflect expected land cover classes, while rows represent actual classes.

		Actual			
		Mangrove	Water	Soil	Vegetation
Predicted	Mangrove	355	15	0	18
	Water	13	355	3	1
	Soil	0	5	367	10
	Vegetation	18	4	17	360

The Indonesian government and the World Bank are working together to restore and safeguard the mangrove ecosystem through the Mangrove for Coastal Resilience Program (M4CR). The 2024 M4CR program focuses on four provinces there are North Sumatra, Riau, North Kalimantan, and East Kalimantan as initiative provinces. The next images show the results of mangrove classification in several cities in the four provinces. Figure 6 shows the classification results in Medan. Medan, a city on the east coast of Sumatra, has several important mangrove areas, although not as extensive as in other places. Based on PMN 2023, the existing mangrove area in North Sumatra is 59765 Ha. In Figure 6 it can be seen that the method developed can detect mangroves quite well in the city of Medan, although the north area is misclassified as vegetation as shown in the red circle.

Fig. 6: Mangrove classification result in Medan – North Sumatera (left image) compared to the OMM 2023(right image).

Figure 7 shows the classification result in Tembilahan – Riau. The existing mangrove over Riau province in 2023 is 231.038 Ha. Tembilahan is the capital of Indragiri Hilir district. The mangrove ecosystem in the city of Tembilahan grows along rivers and coasts. The classification results demonstrate that the proposed algorithm can locate mangroves near rivers in Tembilahan with high accuracy.

Fig. 7: Mangrove detected in Tembilahan – Riau (left image) compared to the OMM 2023 (right image).

Tarakan is the largest city in North Kalimantan and the provincial capital. Geographically, this city borders the Sulawesi Sea and is one of the important gateways to the South China Sea. North Kalimantan has a total of 203.926 ha of mangroves. The green region in Figure 8 depicts the findings of mangrove identification in Tarakan City, while the red area reflects the outcomes of Tarakan City's PMN delineation in 2023.

Fig. 8: Mangrove classification result in Tarakan – North Kalimantan (left image) compared to the OMM 2023 (right image).

Fig. 9: Mangrove detected in Mahakam Delta – East Kalimantan(left image) compared to the OMM 2023 (right image)

The Mahakam Delta is one of the largest river deltas in Indonesia, located in East Kalimantan Province, precisely at the mouth of the Mahakam River. The mangrove in the Mahakam Delta is a very important part of the rich coastal ecosystem in Eastern Kalimantan. Commonly found species include Rhizophora, Avicennia, Sonneratia, and

Bruguiera. The ability of the algorithm to detect mangroves in the Mahakam Delta is shown in Figure 9. The classification results obtained provide a reliable degree of accuracy.

4. Discussion

The preparation of OMM in Indonesia began in 2013 and has been progressively carried out as shown in the following table.

Table 2: Mapped mangrove area during early OMM development.

Year	Area
2013	Jawa
2014	Sumatera
2015	Sulawesi
2016	Bali and Nusa Tenggara Islands
2017	Maluku Islands
2018	Kalimantan
2019	Papua

Table 2 shows the mapped mangrove area during early OMM development. Based on the data shown on the Table 2 above, the first OMM presented about 3.31 million Ha of mangrove cover conditions throughout Indonesia. Based on the data, it was found that 19% of Indonesia's mangrove forest, or about 637.624 Ha is in the sparse and very rare category of vegetation cover. According to SNI 7717 of 2011, the information contained in this first OMM includes 5 canopy density classes, i.e; (a) Very dense mangrove (>90%), (b) Dense mangrove (70-90%), (c) Medium-density mangrove (50-69%), (d) Sparse mangrove (30-49%), and (e) Very rare mangrove (<30%). Nevertheless, since the data collected in preparing the OMM comes from different years, it is difficult to use this data as a reference for initial conditions (baseline) in the planning of programs or activities. So that along the way, some changes were made to get an overview of the current conditions of mangroves in Indonesia on a detailed scale and obtain interpretation results that are more accurate and closer to the real conditions in the field.

In 2020, the SNI 771-2011 was changed to SNI 7712-2020 with three canopy cover classes, i.e;(a) Dense mangrove (70-90%), (b) Medium-density mangrove (30-70%), and (c) Sparse mangrove (0-30%). Furthermore, starting in 2021, an update of the existing mangroves simultaneously spatially for all of Indonesia using remote sensing methods. Since 2019, the maintenance of Mangrove Thematic Geospatial Information has been entrusted to the Directorate of Soil and Water Conservation of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK). In preparing the OMM, KLHK has collaborated with several Indonesian Ministries/Agencies that have the same interests, namely the Geospatial Information Agency (BIG), National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN), the Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries (KKP) and the Peatland and

Mangrove Restoration Agency (BRGM).

The proposed method is the first mangrove detection method that can be used throughout the coastal areas of Indonesia. This method produces a promising level of accuracy. Furthermore, this method can be applied to Landsat-8/9 multitemporal data with different periods. Thus, this method can be utilized in the routine monitoring of mangrove ecosystems in coastal areas and can help expedite and make the creation of the One Map Mangrove Indonesia more efficient.

For research related to mangrove ecosystems, the provided method can be used as a benchmark for similar studies. In addition, the methods produced in this study can be used to analyze and map other species living in that environment. Furthermore, this research can also find out the economic valuation in supporting the economy of the surrounding community. In a broader contribution, through the results of this research, the carbon potential stored in the mangrove ecosystem in Indonesia, which provides global benefits, can be determined.

The method produced in this research can also be applied in other countries that have similar characteristics to the coastal areas of Indonesia. This is because this method has been adapted to the topology and characteristics of coastal areas in all provinces of Indonesia.

Misclassification in mangrove detection may occur due to many circumstances. The possible sources of misclassification include mangroves frequently exhibit spectral signatures akin to other coastal flora, such as nipa palms, halophytic plants, or aquaculture ponds containing algae; high and low tides can either conceal or reveal mangrove habitats, leading to ambiguity between aquatic environments and mangrove zones; and seasonal variations in vegetation density, leaf phenology, and moisture content can modify spectral responses.

Mitigating these sources requires multi-temporal or multi-source data selection, advanced classification techniques, and incorporating ancillary data for more accurate mangrove detection.

Future research of this study may focus on assessing the optimal index to map the mangrove ecosystem throughout Indonesia which can provide a higher degree of accuracy. Apart from that, the OMM development is still very wide open, for example, studies to add socio-economic parameters or geo-biophysical parameters such as mangrove species types are still needed to enrich the OMM produced. Furthermore, the method for mapping mangroves based on species is still challenging. The OMMs that have been produced can also be used as study material in the fields of energy, economics, society, and culture. For example, in the calculation of carbon stocks, rehabilitation plans to preserve the mangrove ecosystem, the economic benefits obtained by communities around the mangrove ecosystems, and many more.

Indonesia is a world leader in mangrove ecosystems,

boasting the highest diversity and the most extensive mangrove cover globally. There are an estimated 45 true mangrove species in Indonesia, out of the 75 found worldwide. This rich biodiversity contributes to the health and functionality of the mangrove forests. Here are some of the common mangrove species found in Indonesia: *Rhizophora* (known locally as bakau): This genus is characterized by prop roots that help them anchor in the soft, muddy soil. There are three species of *Rhizophora* in Indonesia: *Rhizophora apiculata*, *Rhizophora mucronata*, and *Rhizophora stylosa*. *Bruguiera*: This genus has the most species in Indonesia, with six: *Bruguiera cylindrica*, *Bruguiera exaristata*, *Bruguiera gymnorhiza*, *Bruguiera haennessii*, *Bruguiera parviflora*, and *Bruguiera sexangula*. *Bruguiera* trees are known for their knee roots that protrude above the water. Other prominent mangrove species include *Nypa fruticans* (Nipah palm), *Lumnitzera racemosa* (black mangrove), *Ceriops tagal* (grey mangrove), *Xylocarpus granatum* (cannonball mangrove), and *Sonneratia alba* (white mangrove).

Mangrove mapping is a crucial tool for understanding, protecting, and managing these vital ecosystems. By creating maps of mangrove distribution, extent, and health, conservationists and policymakers can: Monitor changes in mangrove cover over time: This allows them to identify areas of deforestation or degradation and take necessary actions. Prioritize conservation efforts: Maps can help identify the most valuable and vulnerable mangrove areas for targeted protection. Support sustainable development: Mangrove maps can inform land-use planning decisions to ensure that development activities minimize impacts on these ecosystems. Improve management of mangrove resources: Maps can be used to identify areas suitable for sustainable harvesting of mangrove products, such as timber and fish. Overall, mangrove mapping is an essential component of conserving and managing Indonesia's precious mangrove ecosystems.

5. Conclusion

The automated mangrove detection method proposed in this study used combined mangrove index and machine learning to detect mangroves over Indonesia. The NDMI and MVI Index from Landsat 8/9 are used to obtain training datasets for the Random Forest process. The Murray global tidal wetland offers maps of the global extent and changes of tidal wetlands, was used to mask the tidal area in Indonesia to increase the accuracy as it can select wetlands areas that are an ecosystem of mangroves. The results showed that the overall accuracy is 0.93, and the kappa accuracy is 0.91. Thus, the proposed method has a high accuracy and can be used as an alternative method for mapping mangroves and non-mangroves, especially in Indonesia.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank and appreciate the anonymous reviewers. The authors would like to thank the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) for providing Landsat 8 and Landsat 9 images, and Google for the GEE platform. The authors also thank the Research Center for Geoinformatics BRIN, the Research Organization for Aeronautics and Space BRIN, and the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) for their support.

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